

Supplementary Materials: A Physics-Informed Multi-Regime Ensemble U-Net Framework for Satellite-Based Water Quality Inversion: Bridging Scale Gaps and Seasonal Non-Stationarity

1. Seasonal triplets map for mean CDOM concentration, CDOM STD and CDOM CV

These triplets serve as an uncertainty budget for the demonstration site, enabling the identification of specific regions where high STD indicates stochastic volatility induced by sensor artefact behaviour, which is a result of low model consensus in the presence of strong spectral noise.

Figure 1: Seasonal CDOM triplets showing the predicted mean concentration, STD and CV throughout the demonstration site - Kastela Bay

2. Distributional estimate for mean CDOM concentration, CDOM STD and CDOM CV

The violin plots describe the estimated distribution range found at the demonstration site for mean CDOM, CDOM STD and CDOM CV.

Figure 2: Seasonal distributional estimate for mean CDOM concentration, CDOM STD and CDOM CV throughout the demonstration site - Kastela Bay

3. Seasonal triplets map for mean TUR concentration, TUR STD and TUR CV

Retrieval of turbidity from Sentinel-2 signal demonstrate a strong stability indicating the PIMREN ability to extract information from the satellite signal during all four seasons.

Figure 3: Seasonal TUR triplets showing the predicted mean concentration, STD and CV throughout the demonstration site - Kastela Bay

4. Distributional estimate for mean TUR concentration, TUR STD and TUR CV

The violin plots describe the estimated distribution range found at the demonstration site for mean TUR, TUR STD and TUR CV.

Figure 4: Seasonal distributional estimate for mean TUR concentration, TUR STD and TUR CV throughout the demonstration site - Kastela Bay